

APPLICATION OF MIXTURE LAW TO RHEOCHOR. PART V. TERNARY MIXTURES

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Application of mixture law to rheochor in binary system of solid-liquid and in ternary system has been investigated.

In a series of papers (*this Journal*, 1944, 21, 30; 1946, 23, 349; 1948, 25, 166, 575; 1949, 26, 533; 1950, 27, 316) we have studied the application of mixture law to rheochor in case of binary liquid-liquid mixtures. This work is being extended. In the mean while the applicability of the law for a binary system of solid-liquid and for a ternary system is being investigated, the preliminary work of which is recorded in this paper. Our investigations will be classified into two main groups of solids-electrolytes and non-electrolytes and each will be studied in associated and non-associated liquids, and in mixtures containing both the associated and non-associated liquids.

In case of liquid mixtures mixing in all proportions, the whole range of molar concentration can be investigated, but in case of solids, the solubility limits the concentration. In general, the solubilities are not high and hence the molar concentrations are low. This introduces a greater error when the rheochor (R_x) is calculated from the mixture law

$$R_m = (1-x) + x R_x.$$

For a ternary mixture, if R_m is the observed rheochor, x - y and $1-x-y$ are the molar fractions of the two solutes and the solvent, and R_x , R_y and R are the respective rheochors, then

$$R_m = (1-x-y) R + x R_x + y R_y.$$

This expression has been used in studying the application of mixture law to ternary mixtures. Similarly,

$$R_m = M_m (10^3 \times \eta)^{1/3} / D$$

where η is the viscosity of the mixture, D , its density, M_m , its mean molecular weight, given by the expression,

$$M_m = (1-x-y) M + x M_x + y M_y$$

where M , M_x and M_y are the molecular weights of the solvent and solutes.

TABLE I

Binary mixtures: Solid-liquid system.

Urea in water.					
x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x
0.0486	1.040	8.72	20.02	25.54	60.9
0.0994	1.076	9.91	22.18	27.46	63.77
0.1318	1.096	10.87	23.54	28.94	65.2

Acetamide in water					
x .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
0.0438	1.009	10.15	19.8	26.2	86
0.0791	1.016	11.78	21.25	28.47	86.98
0.1282	1.023	14.16	23.27	31.67	87.30
Chloral hydrate and water.					
0.0260	1.099	12.76	21.84	27.32	172.2
0.0441	1.158	16.31	24.50	29.99	171.6
0.0600	1.200	18.41	26.87	32.22	169.9

TABLE II
Ternary mixtures.

x .	y .	D .	$\eta \times 10^3$.	M_m .	R_m .	R_x .
Urea (x), acetamide (y) and water.						
0.0258	0.0910	1.035	12.88	22.81	30.31	96.69
0.0479	0.0729	1.048	12.29	23.00	30.15	67.17
0.0858	0.0862	1.070	14.17	25.14	32.74	67.00
0.1174	0.324	1.087	12.82	24.27	30.45	65.45
Acetamide (x), chloral hydrate (y) and water.						
0.0979	0.0255	1.100	16.75	25.79	33.34	85.96
0.0391	0.0549	1.181	18.95	27.71	33.89	83.45
0.0599	0.0428	1.147	18.02	26.77	33.52	85.90
0.1593	0.0119	1.070	18.55	26.29	35.28	86.62
					Average $R_x =$	85.7
Chloral hydrate (x), acetylurea (y) and H_2O .						
0.0494	0.0468	1.193	17.31	27.27	32.63	171.3
0.0343	0.0862	1.171	15.72	26.68	32.20	177.0
0.0286	0.0983	1.162	15.03	26.34	31.81	178.2

The results with ternary mixtures indicate that the values of R_x observed are more or less the same as obtained from binary mixtures. The work is being extended as the preliminary results are promising and the results will be discussed on completion of the investigation.